

MODELLING OF THE WORKPIECE DEFLECTION IN THE CANTILEVER DURING TURNING BY THE METHOD OF NUMERICAL DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS

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ABSTRACT: One of the main factors that adversely affect surface quality, dimensional accuracy, and geometric precision during turning processes is workpiece's deformation. The manufacturer's optimization of the cutting process is crucial. The goal of this work is to model and optimize workpiece's deflection using statistical analysis. The tangential and radial cutting forces were observed as a function of the cutting parameters: cutting speed (V_c in m/min), advance (f in mm/rev), cutting depth (a_p in mm), workpiece hardness (HB), and tool rake angle (A_n) using a numerical experimental plan (DOE) based on the Taguchi L32 table and the finite element analysis (FEA) tool (Third Wave AdvantEdge). For every test, the cantilever beam equation is used to determine the workpiece's deflection, which is then examined using the statistical approach based on the controllable parameters through cutting forces and the workpiece's overhang ratio (L/d). Prediction models have been found for the quantity of interest.

KEYWORDS: machining precision, design of experiments, workpiece deflection, Taguchi, metal cutting simulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Turning is established as a primary metal cutting method, used to manufacture pieces with precise shapes and dimensions (Yousefi & Zohoor, 2018, 2019). Dimensional and geometric precision, as well as surface condition, are the major quality indicators of workpiece (Davakan & El Ouafi, 2017). There are numerous factors affecting this quality, such as tool wear, thermal and mechanical deformation of the elastic system (machine, tool, workpiece, and clamping device) (Slătineanu et al., 2010). The workpiece deflection under cutting forces effect constitutes the major parameter affecting machining tolerances. It has been found that the dimensional deviation is due to the cutting forces during the turning of a slender workpiece, presenting a mathematical model to predict this deviation with a view to developing an adaptive control system (El-Karamany, 1984; Risbood et al., 2003). According to other studies, dimensional inaccuracies are brought on by the tool and workpiece bending, theoretical formulations derived from finite element analysis compared to experimentation have been used to calculate workpiece and tool deflections, other authors have studied geometric errors in turning operations using finite element methods

(Karabulut, 2010; Lee & Lee, 2011; Phan et al., 2003). By considering the deviation of tool, workpiece, and machine-tool, DENKENA et al (Denkena et al., 2017) proposed a technique to compensate geometric errors triggered by cutting forces applied on a cylindrical workpiece. Taking into consideration the stiffness of the machine-tool system, K. Halé et al developed a geometric error estimation model using the GIORLEO model (El-Dahabi et al., 2020). In their comparison of machining accuracy for point-to-point turning, Wu, M. et al discovered that reverse turning reduces machining error for thin shafts (M. Wu & Zhou, 2020). T. Berg et al provided an analytical method for the assessment of dimensional inaccuracies that takes into consideration both tool wear and the elastic deflection of workpiece-tool (Bergs et al., 2021). Numerous works have been conducted to improve the performance of machining processes using statistical methods (Abellan-Nebot & Romero Subirón, 2010; H. Wu et al., 2020). Some of them use regression models and Taguchi analysis to estimate, predict, and enhance machining performance (Bhuiyan, 2019; Mahbubah et al., 2022). Vibrations, torque, cutting forces, temperature, and acoustic emissions have been identified as significant measures influencing

workpiece quality (Pereira Guimaraes et al., 2022; Vacharanukul & Mekid, 2005). S. Balasubramaniyan et al have examined the effect of cutting parameters on circularity and cylindricity during the machining of EN25 steel. The optimization of these parameters was carried out using Taguchi method (Balasubramaniyan & Selvaraj, 2017). Dharet al investigated the impact of minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) on the performance of conventional turning processes. Their findings ultimately indicated that both surface roughness and dimensional accuracy were enhanced(N. Dhar et al., 2007; N. R. Dhar et al., 2006).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that most research has focused on predicting machining performance such as cutting force, roughness, and tool wear based on cutting conditions, without considering the reliability of machine tools and instrumentation, which limits the reliability of the models. Some authors calculate the workpiece's deflection under an empirical cutting force action (cutting manual), using the equation for a simply supported cantilever beam deflection. In this case, the study remains applicable only to the case examined. But in real-time and for the general case, it is the cutting parameters, mechanical characteristics of the materials to be machined, and workpiece's geometry, selected by the manufacturer, that cause this deflection. Practically, since it is challenging to measure piece's deformation during turning process, a combination of analytical and numerical methods as well as experimental concepts are used to predict it.

Nowadays, as computing and analytical techniques have advanced, the numerical simulation of the required cutting process, including statistics and cutting force, has become a crucial tool for solving such problems more quickly and at a lower cost than real experiments (Hu et al., 2020; Korkmaz & Günay, 2018). Therefore, it is essential to conduct an in-depth study on the influence of cutting parameters, tool cutting angle, materials and workpiece's geometry on its deflection.

Since the improvement of machining process performance inevitably involves the optimization of machining process and the reduction of workpiece's deflection, it becomes important to analyze the influence of cutting parameters, material to be machined, tool's cutting angle, and the workpiece's overhang L/d ratio on its deflection, using numerical experimental design method based on Taguchi design.

By analyzing the main input parameters impact on workpiece's deformation, we aim to build mathematical models that can forecast workpiece's

deflection during turning process. Therefore, our goal is to provide manufacturers with accurate and universal predictive models so they can guarantee the machining process's capabilities and uphold dimensional tolerances.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology adopted the following steps:

Using a specific FEA tool (Third Wave AdvantEdge) for metal cutting, the cutting process was first done through simulation. A virtual experimental design based on the Taguchi L32(2⁵) table was used in this process to monitor cutting forces as a function of cutting parameters, tool cutting angle, and the workpiece's material hardness.

Simultaneously, the workpiece's deflection was calculated using a basic cantilever beam model under the action of the resultant R of the cutting forces FX and Fy by varying its cantilever length. This deflection was then determined using the Taguchi L32 (2⁶) method based on the controllable input parameters through the cutting force and its cantilever length.

The statistical analysis was conducted using Minitab version 19.

2.1 Materials

The materials used are, AISI 1020 and AISI 1045 steels, whose chemical compositions and mechanical characteristics are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1 Chemical compositions of AISI 1020 and AISI 1045 steels

Materials	Mn%	C%	S%	P%
AISI 1045	0.78	0.461	0.05	0.05
AISI 1020	0.4	70.21	0.051	0.04

Table 2 Mechanical characteristics of AISI 1045 steels and AISI 1020

Materials	AISI 1020	AISI 1045
Ultimate stress σ (MPa)	395	1027
Yield stress V (MPa)	295	612
Hardness Brinell HB	111	305
Young's Modulus E(Gpa)	200	200

2.2 Taguchi Methodology

Taguchi method is a statistical tool that relies on fractional experimental designs. It allows analyzing the simultaneous impact of several variables on a given response. With this approach, a set of parameters can be examined to optimize the process

in question. The DOE is an efficient method in terms of time and cost (Chaib et al., 2024; C. Sumesh & Ramesh, 2023; C. S. Sumesh et al., 2021; C. S. Sumesh & Ramesh, 2018). All parameters as well as their levels are recorded in a combination table (OA). A Taguchi plan is designed to observe F_x , F_y through simulation based on: cutting speed (V_c), cutting depth (a_p), feed (f), Brinell hardness (HB) of the workpiece, cutting angle (A_n). According to the Taguchi L32 plan, each factor has two levels and the effects of these factors as well as the L/d ratio of the workpiece on its bending (Table 3). Tables were used to present the findings of the numerical tests for analyzing the resultant force R , as well as the simulated cutting forces F_x and F_y , and the calculated values of the workpiece's deformation. In Taguchi method, signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios are used to evaluate the results of optimal process parameter adjustments, based on experimental data. S and N illustrate the desired (mean) and undesirable (standard deviation) values for the produced responses. The values are represented in accordance with the condition "the better, the smaller" for the workpiece deflection. It presents the optimal performance of a delta rank parameter for controllable input variables. The S/N ratio (dB) is calculated using equation (1) (lower the better).

$$\eta = \frac{S}{N_S} = -10 \log \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

Where Y_i is the i -th value of the calculated characteristic (efficiency).

2.3 Cutting tool

In 2D orthogonal cutting simulations (figure 1), standard carbide inserts were employed as the cutting tools, using a nose radius r of 0.02 mm, a clearance angle b equal to 5, a positive cutting angle of 5, and a negative angle of -5.

2.4 FEM Simulations

A virtual machining operation was carried out on AISI 1045 and AISI 1020 steels using Third Wave AdvantEdge program (figure 3), which simulates metal cutting with an arbitrary Lagrangian solver. The configuration of the mesh of the workpiece and cutting tool is simulated with a maximum and a minimum tool element dimensions of 0.1 mm and 0.02 mm, respectively, as well as a mesh size of 0.4 mm. At the initial stage of simulations, workpiece's model dimensions were 5 mm in length and 2 mm in height. The second step is to define the material to be machined. The cutting angle, clearance angle, edge radius, and tool material characteristics are defined in the third phase. After modifying the mesh parameters and the friction coefficient, the required

cutting simulation parameters, such as, feed rate, cutting depth, initial temperature, and cutting speed, are entered into the software in the last stage. For the 2D simulations, the interface between the tool and the workpiece was modeled with a standard Coulomb friction coefficient assumed to be equal to 0.6 (figure 2). The numerical results were extracted following the completion of the process. Figure 3 illustrates the 2D orthogonal cutting model. The L32 (2^5) Taguchi design matrix is used to select the state of the process parameters for conducting simulation tests.

Fig. 1 Adjusting cutting parameters and tool geometry

Fig. 2 Model simulation

Fig. 3 Cutting simulation flowchart by AdvanEdge software

F_x, F_y function of (V_c, f, a_p, HB, A_n)

Workpiece deflection function of ($V_c, f, a_p, HB, A_n, L/d$).

Table 3 level table of parameters controllable

Factors	Level 1	Level 2
Cutting speed V_c (m/min)	50	150
Feed f (mm/rev)	0.1	0.3
depth of Cutting a_p (mm)	1	2
Brinell hardness (HB)	111	305
Ranke angle A_n (degré)	-5	5
Workpiece fraction (L/d)	1,5	2,5

for (F_x, F_y) observed and reponse Workpiece deflection

2.5 Calculation of the workpiece deflection for each test

The workpiece's deflection is estimated using the basic cantilever beam model (figure 4). The cutting force R , resulting from F_x and F_y , is applied to the workpiece at the end that is L distant from the chuck. The piece deflection for each combination is calculated using the Excel tool in accordance with the Taguchi L32 (2^6) table. The statistical method is then applied based on the cutting parameters, the cutting angle, the Brinell hardness of the material to be machined, and the ratio of its overhang.

Fig. 4 Illustration of the workpiece's deflection calculation

$$\text{WorkpieceDeflection} = \frac{R.L^3}{3.E.I} \quad (2)$$

$$R = \sqrt{F_x'^2 + F_y'^2} \quad (3)$$

$$I = \frac{\pi.D^4}{64} \quad (4)$$

length: 30, 50 mm

workpiece diameter: 20 mm

3 RESULTS AND DISCUTIONS

3.1 Simulation outcomes

In test 14 (Table 4), the eleventh trial of combinations from the Taguchi table was simulated, and the graph shows the outcomes of the tangential and radial cutting forces F_x and F_y filtered polynomially by determining their resultant R . Using the equation for the deflection of a simply supported cantilever beam and the analytical approach, the results are gathered in a text file and processed by Excel. The table displays the 32 tests results.

Fig. 5 Simulation Results test 14 of tangential and radial cutting force F_x, F_y .

Table 4 Responses R and workpiece deflection test results in accordance with Taguchi L32

Tests	RN	Workpiece Deflection mm	S/B Worpiece Deflection
1	321,34	0,0018421	54,6939

2	244,99	0,0065018	43,7393
3	457,79	0,0121494	38,3089
4	381,29	0,0021857	53,2081
5	642,76	0,0170584	35,3613
6	490,42	0,0028113	51,0218
7	915,49	0,0052480	45,6001
8	769,26	0,0204157	33,8007
9	804,40	0,0213482	33,4128
10	636,72	0,0036500	48,7542
11	1057,65	0,0060629	44,3463
12	880,17	0,0233591	32,6309
13	1608,65	0,0092216	40,7039
14	1273,43	0,0337959	29,4227
15	2111,34	0,0560335	25,0310
16	1760,96	0,0100947	39,9182
17	300,42	0,0079730	41,9676
18	241,95	0,0013870	57,1588
19	428,34	0,0024554	52,1975
20	364,31	0,0096686	40,2927
21	601,07	0,0034456	49,2546
22	479,94	0,0279840	31,0618
23	856,82	0,0227394	32,8644
24	729,31	0,0041808	47,5749
25	775,99	0,0044483	47,0361
26	631,19	0,0167513	35,5191
27	1009,00	0,0267780	31,4444
28	863,51	0,0049500	46,1078
29	1551,94	0,0411875	27,7047
30	1257,90	0,0072109	42,8402
31	2014,66	0,0115490	38,7491
32	1711,98	0,0454347	26,8522

Fig. 6 Impact of input parameters on the workpiece deflection degree

3.3 Signal/noise ratio main effects plot for workpiece deflection

Based on statistical analysis, the signal/noise ratio (S/N) and the average values of the quality characteristics were calculated using Minitab19 software.

3.3.1 Main effects of workpiece deflection

The main effects represented by response curves, were used to evaluate the impact of the parameters on the response characteristics. The average values of workpiece's deflection for each process parameter across the stages are shown in figure 7 and presented in table 5, which indicates that Vc has no effect on the piece's deflection but increases as f, ap, HB, and L/d increase and decreases when An is positive.

Fig. 7 Main effect plot for means workpiece Deflection

3.2 Variance analysis (ANOVA)

According to the ANOVA results (Figure 6), the L/d ratio has the greatest impact on the piece's deviation at 49.40%, followed by f (15.62%) and ap (14.40%). The material hardness was 1.66 %. Conversely, the effects of An and Vc are insignificant, with 0.44% and 0.02%, respectively.

Table 6 Main effects Plot for Signal Noise Ratio S/N for workpiece deflection

Level	Vc	f	ap	HB	An	L/d
1	0,014 486	0,009 253	0,009 469	0,012 914	0,015 596	0,005 046

2	0,014 884	0,020 117	0,019 901	0,016 457	0,013 774	0,024 324
Del ta	0,000 398	0,010 864	0,010 431	0,003 543	0,001 822	0,019 277
Ra nk	6	2	3	4	5	1

4 REGRESSION MODELS

4.1 Model with principal factors

The objective is to determine the appropriate model that expresses the factor of interest (workpiece deviation) as a function of the process input variables and to perform an analysis of the first-degree linear model without interactions.

$$\text{Workpiece deflection} = -0,05458 + 0,000004Vc + 0,0543f + 0,01043ap + 0,000018HB - 0,000182An + 0,01928L/d \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 81,34\%$$

4.2 Model with main factors and influential interactions

Regression models considering only significant parameters and interactions

$$\text{Workpiece deflection} = 0,0372 - 0,1479.f - 0,02384.ap - 0,000046 HB + 0,000238. An - 0,01949 L/d + 0,0297. f*ap + 0,000118 f*HB - 0,00210 f*An + 0,0666 f*L/d + 0,01417 ap*L/d + 0,000020 HB*L/d \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 96,78 \%$$

By fixing the level of the independent variables at the center of the experimental domain, it is possible to track the evolution of the other two variables and their influence on the responses. Graphs are used to visualize and determine the best conditions to minimize the workpiece's deformation within the defined study domain.

The predicted curve and the experimental one are highly compatible (figure 9).

Fig. 9 Comparison of the workpiece deflection's observed and predicted values

Fig. 10 2D or contour plots for Workpiece deflection

The graphs in Figure 10 can be used to visualize and determine the best conditions for minimizing workpiece distortion within the designated research range. Fixing the level of the independent variables in the center of the experimental field permits to track the development of the other two variables and their impact on the responses.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The main focus of this work was on the impact of cutting parameters, the hardness of the material to be machined, tool cutting angle, and workpiece overhang on workpiece deflection. A signal-to-noise analysis was used to identify the best factors for lowering the workpiece's deflection, with the lowest values preferred. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was then used to look at how these factors affected the outcomes, and the following conclusions were reached:

With a 49.40% contribution, the L/d ratio was shown to have the largest impact on the piece's deflection, followed by the feed rate (15.62%) and cutting depth (14.40%), next, the hardness of the material at 1.66%. While the cutting angle and speed contributes nearly nothing, at 0.44% and 0.02%, respectively;

There is a very slight deviation in the workpiece when the input variables are set to the following values: $Vc = 150$ m/min, $f = 0.1$ mm/min, $ap = 1$ mm, $HB = 111$, $An = 5$ degrees, and $L/a = 1.5$;

-With strong main factors and factor interactions, the model's linear regression produced a very good prediction for the piece ($R^2 = 96.78 \%$);

By converting the workpiece's deflection into geometric and diametrical errors, the model will assist the manufacturer in anticipating workpiece deviation and preventing waste.

6 REFERENCES

Abellan-Nebot, J. V., & Romero Subirón, F. (2010). A review of machining monitoring systems based on artificial intelligence process models. The

- International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 47, 237–257.
- Balasubramaniyan, S., & Selvaraj, T. (2017). Application of integrated Taguchi and TOPSIS method for optimization of process parameters for dimensional accuracy in turning of EN25 steel. *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, 40(4), 267–274.
- Bergs, T., Knappe, D., Husseini, K., Pullen, T., Schraknepper, D., & Döring, J.-E. (2021). Investigation of the diameter error when turning thin walled workpieces. *Procedia CIRP*, 102, 343–348.
- Bhuiyan, M. S. H. (2019). Minimization of Cutting Force by Optimizing the Cutting Parameters Using Taguchi Method in Turning. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 530(1), 12006.
- Chaib, B., Brioua, M., Baiti, A., & Banarioua, M. (2024). Modeling and optimization of cutting force and tool deformation by the method of numerical design of experiments using the Taguchi method. *Studies in Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 5(2), e7845–e7845.
- Davakan, D. M., & El Ouafi, A. (2017). Artificial neural networks based integrated predictive modelling of quality characteristics in CNC turning of cantilever bars. *World Journal of Mechanics*, 7(05), 143.
- Denkena, B., Dahlmann, D., Peters, R., & Witt, M. (2017). Model based compensation of geometrical deviations due to process forces. *Journal of Machine Engineering*, 17.
- Dhar, N., Islam, S., & Kamruzzaman, M. (2007). Effect of minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) on tool wear, surface roughness and dimensional deviation in turning AISI-4340 steel. *Gazi University Journal of Science*, 20(2), 23–32.
- Dhar, N. R., Islam, M. W., Islam, S., & Mithu, M. A. H. (2006). The influence of minimum quantity of lubrication (MQL) on cutting temperature, chip and dimensional accuracy in turning AISI-1040 steel. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 171(1), 93–99.
- El-Dahabi, F., Dib, R., Abou-El-Hossein, K., Hatefi, S., Abbas, A., & Hweju, Z. (2020). Effect of machine-tool rigidity on geometric error formation in turning operation. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics Research*, 9(5).
- El-Karamany, Y. (1984). Turning long workpieces by changing the machining parameters. *International Journal of Machine Tool Design and Research*, 24(1), 1–10.
- Hu, Z., Zhang, W., Li, X., & Gao, H. (2020). The cutting force simulation of 30CrMnSiA based on AdvantEdge 2D broaching. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1601(4), 42022.
- Karabulut, A. (2010). Determination of diametral error using finite elements and experimental method. *Metalurgija-Zagreb*, 49(1), 57.
- Korkmaz, M. E., & Günay, M. (2018). Finite element modelling of cutting forces and power consumption in turning of AISI 420 martensitic stainless steel. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 43, 4863–4870.
- Lee, M., & Lee, C. (2011). Development of analysis model for geometric error in turning processes. *Journal of Central South University*, 18(3), 711–717.
- Mahbubah, N. A., Nuruddin, M., Dahda, S. S., Andesta, D., Ismiyah, E., Widyaningrum, D., Fathoni, M. Z., Kurniawan, M. D., Rizqi, A. W., & Priatna, E. D. (2022). Optimization of CNC turning parameters for cutting Al6061 to achieve good surface roughness based on Taguchi method. *Journal of Advanced Research in Applied Mechanics*, 99(1), 1–9.
- Pereira Guimaraes, B. M., da Silva Fernandes, C. M., Amaral de Figueiredo, D., Correia Pereira da Silva, F. S., & Macedo Miranda, M. G. (2022). Cutting temperature measurement and prediction in machining processes: comprehensive review and future perspectives. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 120(5), 2849–2878.
- Phan, A.-V., Baron, L., Mayer, J. R. R., & Cloutier, G. (2003). Finite element and experimental studies of diametral errors in cantilever bar turning. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 27(3), 221–232.
- Risbood, K. A., Dixit, U. S., & Sahasrabudhe, A. D. (2003). Prediction of surface roughness and dimensional deviation by measuring cutting forces and vibrations in turning process. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 132(1–3), 203–214.
- Slătineanu, L., Coteață, M., Beșliu-Grigoraș, I., & Boca, M. (2010). Elastic deflection of the cylindrical work pieces during the machining. *Proceedings in Manufacturing Systems*, 5(1), 1–6.
- Sumesh, C., & Ramesh, A. (2023). Optimization and finite element modeling of orthogonal turning of Ti6Al4V alloys: A comparative study of different optimization techniques. *Engineering Solid Mechanics*, 11(1), 11–22.
- Sumesh, C. S., Akbar, D. S., Purandharadass, H. S., & Chandrasekaran, R. J. (2021). Optimization of dimensional tolerances and material removal rate in the orthogonal turning of AISI 4340 steel. *Periodica*

Polytechnica Mechanical Engineering, 65(3), 205–216.

Sumesh, C. S., & Ramesh, A. (2018). Numerical modelling and optimization of dry orthogonal turning of Al6061 T6 alloy. *Periodica Polytechnica Mechanical Engineering*, 62(3), 196–202.

Vacharanukul, K., & Mekid, S. (2005). In-process dimensional inspection sensors. *Measurement*, 38(3), 204–218.

Wu, H., Zheng, H., Li, X., Wang, W., Xiang, X., & Meng, X. (2020). A geometric accuracy analysis and tolerance robust design approach for a vertical machining center based on the reliability theory. *Measurement*, 161, 107809.

Wu, M., & Zhou, T. (2020). Analysis of turning process of slim shaft based on finite element method. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1550(4), 42022.

Yousefi, S., & Zohoor, M. (2018). Experimental studying of the variations of surface roughness and dimensional accuracy in dry hard turning operation. *The Open Mechanical Engineering Journal*, 12(1), 175–191.

Yousefi, S., & Zohoor, M. (2019). Effect of cutting parameters on the dimensional accuracy and surface finish in the hard turning of MDN250 steel with cubic boron nitride tool, for developing a knowledge base expert system. *International Journal of Mechanical and Materials Engineering*, 14, 1–13.

7 NOTATION

F_x , F_y : Simulated of tangential and radial cutting force

R : resultant of F_x and F_y

L : Tool extension length

E : Young's modulus of the tool body N/mm^2

D : workpiece diameter

I : Polar quadratic moment cylinder mm^4